

DIGITAL DIPLOMACY AS AN ELEMENT OF MODERN DIPLOMATIC ACTS

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Annotation: Digital diplomacy is mainly practical in nature and is especially useful in working with foreign audiences, expressing the official position and shaping the state's image. The purpose of this scientific work is to theoretically analyze that digital diplomacy is an important factor of political relations in modern life. The task of the scientific work is to reveal in the interpretation the opinions of scientists on the important characteristics of digital diplomacy.

Index Terms – Digital diplomacy, digital act, E-diplomacy, government agencies, social network, media, amplification, criticism, promotion, interaction, communication technologies

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of "digital diplomacy" was created at the beginning of the 21st century. Its appearance was due to the rapid development of science and technology, as a result of which now diplomacy must take into account a powerful tool that quickly captures public opinion - electronic media.

Digital (electronic) diplomacy (English digital diplomacy, e-diplomacy) is the use of the Internet and information and communication technologies (ICT) to solve diplomatic problems. As part of digital diplomacy, new media, social networks, blogs and similar media platforms in the global network are used. E-diplomacy involves government departments, primarily foreign policy, government agencies, as well as non-governmental organizations whose activities are related to the

implementation of the foreign policy agenda.

These questions can be discussed in the research:

- What is digital diplomacy?
- What is the role of digital diplomacy in modern diplomatic relations?
- What are the elements of digital diplomacy?

The answers to these questions are shown below in the theoretical analysis within the theme.

II. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

The main goals of digital diplomacy are the promotion of foreign policy interests, information propaganda through Internet television, social networks and mobile phones, aimed at mass consciousness and political elites.¹

According to N.A. Tsvetkova, digital diplomacy can be viewed as a “government mechanism for influencing users of social networks”². The author argues that the process of developing digital diplomacy consists of two stages:

1. 2009–2012. At that time, digital diplomacy contributed to the realization of a positive image of the state, and "soft power", the purpose of which is to attract the target audience through persuasion, dialogue, etc., was used as an imperative.
2. 2013–2017. In this period, new methods of studying the behavior of the audience in social networks are being developed. This has made digital diplomacy an effective tool for political campaigns, elections or protests.

O.N. Tsvetkova, characterizing digital diplomacy as a whole as a new type of

¹https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%A6%D0%B8%D1%84%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%D1%8F_%D0%B4%D0%B8%D0%BF%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%BC%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%B8%D1%8F

² Tsvetkova, N.A. The phenomenon of digital diplomacy in international relations and the methodology of its study / N.A. Tsvetkova // Bulletin of the Russian State University for the Humanities. — 2020 №2. - S. 46.

diplomacy of the 21st century, argues that:

“— Firstly, the source of digital diplomacy is non-governmental and network organizations that more effectively cover a certain part of the foreign audience with their influence;

— Secondly, the platform for digital diplomacy is the Internet, where news and music formats of radio and television programs are transferred, promotion of the image of a country or organization, etc.;

— Thirdly, members of foreign non-governmental organizations, Internet users in general and young people in particular are becoming the main target groups for digital diplomacy.³”

The researcher also identifies the main, in her opinion, methods for implementing the tasks of digital policy:

— criticism of political life in another country. This helps to attract users and increase their reach;

— amplification of polar opinions in matters of politics and other spheres of society's life contributes to an increase in the intensity of the discussion of a particular problem, drawing more attention to it;

— promotion of a hashtag containing details of a resonant issue;

— interaction with representatives of different political parties of another country⁴.

Tsvetkova also considers digital diplomacy from the point of view of a scientific approach, noting the main methods of its analysis and characterizing them:

³ Tsvetkova, N.A. The phenomenon of digital diplomacy in international relations and the methodology of its study / N.A. Tsvetkova // Bulletin of the Russian State University for the Humanities. — 2020 №2. - S. 46.

⁴ Tsvetkova, N.A. The phenomenon of digital diplomacy in international relations and the methodology of its study / N.A. Tsvetkova // Bulletin of the Russian State University for the Humanities. — 2020 №2. - S. 46.

— hashtag analysis. It helps to identify how the discussion process is developing, what content is most interesting to the audience and which of the participants in the discussion is the most popular among users;

— sentiment analysis. It determines the nature of the reaction of users to published content or information campaigns, which, in turn, helps to identify the identification of the audience and their political views;

— network analysis. Thanks to it, it is possible to identify key bloggers and international channels that create informational discourse;

— analysis of the opinions and views of the audience. This method involves working with texts on Internet sites and social networks, which consists in studying the most commonly used words and phrases. This, in turn, helps build knowledge about the content of posts and comments⁵.

F. Hanson defines digital diplomacy as “the use of the World Wide Web and new ICTs to help achieve foreign policy goals”⁶.

I.V. Surma considers this type of diplomacy as "the wide use of information and communication technologies, including new media, social networks, blogs and similar media platforms in the global network to assist government agencies in the performance of functions and communications on issues related to foreign politics, including mechanisms of influence on foreign audiences”⁷.

E. Zinoviev, in turn, gives an interpretation of digital diplomacy, similar to the definition of I.V. Surma: “the use of information and communication technologies to assist state bodies in the exercise of their functions and to advice on foreign

⁵ Tsvetkova, N.A. The phenomenon of digital diplomacy in international relations and the methodology of its study / N.A. Tsvetkova // Bulletin of the Russian State University for the Humanities. — 2020 №2. - S. 46.

⁶ Hanson, F. Public diplomacy and information management / Hanson, F. URL: <http://egov.by/themes/best-practices/osnovy-ediplomacy-chast-3> (Accessed: 04/02/2021).

⁷ Surma, I.V. Digital diplomacy in world politics / I.V. Surma // Public administration. Electronic Bulletin. - 2015 No. 49. - S. 235.

policy issues. For the first time this type of diplomacy was used by the United States, but today it is widely used by a number of other states.⁸”

According to K.A. Torshina, in the modern discourse of studying digital diplomacy, it is optimal to single out the following areas:

- the tone of communication with the audience;
- goals of the addresser;
- a pool of communication strategies and tactics;
- methods for implementing strategies and tactics;
- tools for implementing strategies and tactics⁹.

III. METHODOLOGY

All the directions listed by the researcher, in fact, are components that must be taken into account when developing a strategy for the functioning of digital diplomacy of a particular country.

The term can be found in the works of E.S. Zinovieva: “Digital diplomacy is one of the areas of public diplomacy, focused on involving the general population in diplomatic practice, and not on interaction with the political and diplomatic elites of foreign states”¹⁰. Today, one can observe how social networks and other platforms are increasingly being used as political propaganda tools. Their main advantage is not only dialogue with the audience, but also the ability to receive instant feedback. The interaction of the first persons of states and various representatives of departments responsible for foreign policy through the Internet and social networks receives great attention and, of course, opens up new

⁸ Zinoviev, E.S. International information security / Zinovieva, E.S. - M.: MGIMO-University, 2013. - S. 145.

⁹ Torshina, K.A. Features of the discourse of digital diplomacy at the present stage / K.A.Torshina // Communicology: electronic scientific journal. — 2019 №3. - S. 33.

¹⁰ Zinov'eva E.S. Tsifrovaya diplomatiya SShA: vozmozhnosti i ugrozy dlya mezhdunarodnoy bezopasnosti, [Digital Diplomacy of the United States: Opportunities and threats to International security]. Indexes Security [Security Index]. 2013, I. 1(104), 215 p.

communication potential. Now, one of the most effective and relevant ways to interact with the electorate is to conduct live online debates or contact Internet users directly. The digital model of diplomacy is moving further and further away from the traditional one. If earlier diplomats communicated with the public through various printed publications or public speeches, now interaction is possible online, in an interactive and often informal manner, which allows you to quickly set an informative picture and set the agenda¹¹. It is worth noting that the model of digital diplomacy is practically not regulated by international legal acts, including the Vienna Convention of Diplomatic Relations. For this reason, digital diplomacy can form its own trends, such as freer and more informal communication. However, foreign affairs departments create instructions that indicate to employees the limits of what is permitted. After all, just one “tweet” that is erroneous or incomprehensible in its wording can not only cause a negative reaction and a stream of criticism, but also provoke an unstable world and economic situation¹². Enormous opportunities for diplomacy lie in developing the potential for multilateral engagement, communication, information and exchange, and analysis of overseas audiences. For this reason, the issue of the ability of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to adapt to new channels of communication and communication in the field of ICT is so important¹³. From an applied point of view, most likely, everything will come down to the fact that the departments of foreign affairs agencies responsible for information technology will become active, if not key, participants in the strategic planning process. It can be foreseen

¹¹ Shakirov O. Budushchee tsifrovoy diplomatii 2018 g. [The Future of Digital Diplomacy]. Available at <https://www.csr.ru/ru/news/budushhee-tsifrovoj-diplomatii/> (Accessed: 06.02.2021).

¹² Tsvetkova N.A. Programma WEB 2.0 v publichnoy diplomatii SShA [Web 2.0 Programs in US Public Diplomacy]. SShA. Kanada : ekonomika, politika, kul'tura. [Usa and Canada: economics, politics, culture,] 2011, I. 3, pp. 109-122. (In Russian).

¹³https://siu.ranepa.ru/sveden/education/annot/2018/Annot_41.03.05_MO_MP_20.9.17_ad.pdf?utm_source=google.com&utm_medium=organic&utm_campaign=google.com&utm_referrer=google.com.

that new formats of digital, both internal and external, diplomatic communication will soon appear, which will entail increased requirements for information culture. Thus, we conclude that all authors understand digital diplomacy as the use of information and communication technologies, including various Internet platforms and social networks, to assist state bodies in their communication on issues related to the foreign policy of the state.

I.Sh. Shamugia emphasizes that the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which have become a prerequisite for the formation of digital diplomacy, contributes to the erasure of national borders and has a serious impact on all spheres of life of the society of any state⁸⁰. From this point of view, the author interprets digital diplomacy as ¹⁴"the use of social networks and the possibilities of the Internet in the diplomatic practice of the government to assist state bodies in matters related to foreign policy, including mechanisms for influencing foreign audiences."

The researcher also draws attention to the relatively recent concept of "public diplomacy": it characterizes the possibility of using social networks by foreign affairs agencies, government agencies, presidents, ministers, and diplomats.

Thanks to this, these entities can publish various information that is in the public domain and capable of influencing a foreign audience in a certain way.

This influence, of course, has its own specific goals. E. Zinovieva formulates them as follows:

- implementation and protection of foreign policy interests of the state;
- Internet propaganda through social networks¹⁵.

I.V. Surma, in turn, noting that digital diplomacy is a form of public diplomacy,

¹⁴ Шамугия, И.Ш. Понятие «публичная дипломатия» в теории международных отношений / И.Ш. Шамугия // Актуальные проблемы современных международных отношений. — 2017 №10. — С. 138.

¹⁵ Zinoviev, E.S. International information security / Zinovieva, E.S. - M.: MGIMO-University, 2013. - S. 130.

highlights from this point of view several methods for achieving its goals:

- placement of radio and TV programs on the Internet;
- distribution of relevant literature in digital format;
- analysis of discussions in blogs;
- creation of personal accounts of leaders, representatives, state bodies of the country in social networks¹⁶.

In addition, the author emphasizes that the way information is presented on the official pages and websites of various state bodies related to foreign policy strongly influences the opinion of citizens of other countries about this state.

IV. RESULTS

As a result, the research was come to the conclusion that the ongoing technological and content revolution in the mass media complicates the interaction of participants in international relations in a number of key indicators. The unprecedented format of close interaction between society and diplomatic departments makes modern diplomacy overly public, on the one hand, and less restrained, on the other.

In these circumstances, it is very important not to lose the information initiative and use new modern means of communication with their specific style of communication, not to allow the level of political culture to fall. Under the fall of the level of political culture I.V. Surma implies methods of conducting network wars, and in general such wars themselves, between countries.

Researcher Shahud Ziad also writes about the use of digital diplomacy as a method of conducting an information war. He points out that “digital diplomacy has become indispensable a communication tool of international relations that allows, on the one hand, to form public opinion about the foreign policy activities

¹⁶ Сурма, И.В. Цифровая дипломатия в мировой политике / И.В. Сурма // Государственное управление. Электронный вестник. — 2015 №49. — С. 236.

of the state, and on the other hand, to resist such new forms of international conflicts as information network wars. It is emphasized that the main feature of digital diplomacy, in contrast to the traditional, classical and “pre-Internet” tools of diplomatic work, is its focus on the general population, and not only and not so much on the diplomatic and political elite of states”¹⁷.

K.A. Torshina defines the main platforms where the digital diplomacy of the state is implemented:

- 1) official websites of leaders, representatives, state bodies of the country;
- 2) personal blogs of leaders and state representatives;
- 3) accounts in social networks;
- 4) electronic media of the country (magazines, newspapers, news agencies)⁸⁴.

The researcher also describes a pool of communication strategies, characteristic of digital diplomacy, structuring everything in a table:

Table 1. Strategies of Digital Diplomacy

Strategies	Characteristics
1. Communication Strategy	Non-evaluative (neutral) coverage of events corresponding to the subject of the Information source
2. Evaluation Strategy	Based on the use of value assessment tools
a. Defamation Strategy	An implicit or explicit appeal to negatively perceived values.
b. Positive representation Strategy	Refers to the positive meanings and emotions of the addressees based on the value orientations
3. Argumentation Strategy	Based on the use of argumentation

¹⁷ Shahud, Z. Digital diplomacy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation in the countries of the Arab world / Z. Shahud //Society: politics, economics, law. - 2019 No. 10 (75). - S. 16.

	tools: eyewitness, accounts, citation, digital evidence, etc
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K.A. Torshina, unlike E. Zinovieva, identifies more tasks that should be implemented by the actors of digital diplomacy - those who communicate on the Web on behalf of the country:

- ensuring the safety of citizens of their country abroad;
- collection and analysis of information in the media;
- formation of a positive image of the country;
- carrying out explanatory work;
- information propaganda¹⁸.

K. Kokoeva, speaking about the functions of digital diplomacy in the foreign policy of the state, formulates its goal as follows: “The goal of digital diplomacy is to lobby the interests of the state in the framework of the foreign policy dialogue with the leaders of foreign states and the public¹⁹. Thus, the goals of digital diplomacy repeat the goals of the foreign policy of the state. However, digital diplomacy is distinguished by its own system of methods and tools that are used to advance the interests of the state.” In general, the author identifies digital and public diplomacy, arguing that the latter has been transformed into the former as a result of the development of information systems and the digitalization of all spheres of society. As a result, the researcher comes to the conclusion that the result of the influence of digital diplomacy on the country's foreign policy is "increasing the information transparency of politicians' activities", erasing the boundaries between politicians and the population, that is, leveling the

¹⁸ Torshina, K.A. Features of the discourse of digital diplomacy at the present stage / K.A. Torshina // Communicology: electronic scientific journal. — 2019 №3. - S. 33.

¹⁹ Kokoeva, K. Digital diplomacy as an instrument of foreign policy / K. Kokoeva // Skif. Issues of student science. - 2020 No. 5 (45). - S. 323.

communication model according to the "top-down" system, increasing the level of political literacy of the people.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are several general areas where digital diplomacy is particularly effective as a foreign ministry resource.

First and foremost, it's public diplomacy: by building relationships with online audiences and creating new communication tools, digital diplomacy allows you to reach target audiences directly with specific messages, including engaging influencers. . Electronic diplomacy promotes citizen-to-citizen and person-to-person communication formats. This dialogue can be initiated by civil society members themselves, and by the state, which can be a moderator in the dialogue.

In the field of information management, including the management of accumulated knowledge and experience: collection and analysis of a large amount of data that can be successfully used in political forecasts and strategic planning. Thanks to modern ICT, the experience and information gathered by various departments of the state foreign policy structures can be successfully used in different parts of the world, regardless of the location of the original source and user.

Consular activities: registration and preparation of visa documents, direct contacts with foreign citizens. In the event of emergencies and natural disasters: use of ICT for emergency communication with the government's embassy abroad.

Based on the above directions, digital diplomacy is mainly of a practical nature, and is especially useful in working with foreign audiences, announcing the official position and shaping the state's image. It is important to understand that diplomacy in the traditional sense is unlikely to be replaced. Closed negotiations remain closed. However, digital diplomacy is able to explain why a certain decision was made, what results it will produce, how it affects the foreign policy process, that is, it reveals public access to the results of traditional diplomacy.

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